

Table 2. Primary data information, 2022. See Table 1 for details.

ID	Date	Author(s)	Time	TZ	Location	State	GPS	s (m)	h (m)
s2523ul	22/05/23	OM	20:55	EDT	Congaree National Park	SC		0.9	0.6
s2524ur	22/05/24	RJ	21:22	EDT	Beaver Pond Nature Trail, Hard Labor Creek State Park	GA	33.672 -83.6113	1.3	0.6
s2524ul	22/05/24	OM, RS	20:50	EDT	Congaree National Park	SC	33.840091 -80.860231	1.5	0.6
s2528ul	22/05/28	OM, RS	21:00	EDT	Congaree National Park	SC	33.839840 -80.860555	1.8	0.6
s2529ul	22/05/29	OM, RS	21:02	EDT	Congaree National Park	SC	33.840025 -80.860314	1.5	0.3
s2601ur	22/06/01	RJ	21:25	EDT	Harris Shoals Park, Watkinsville	GA	33.8641398, -83.4224346	0.9	2.4
s2607ia	22/06/07	RJ	21:07	EDT	Ashmore Heritage Preserve, Cleveland	SC	35.087 -82.5799	1.2	0.6
s2607ic	22/06/07	CM	21:46	EDT	Rome	OH		0.9	0.6
s2609ic	22/06/09	CM	21:44	EDT	Rome	OH		0.9	1.2
s2609io	22/06/09	AO		EDT	Smith-Andover Land, Lincoln	MA	42.4257, -71.30665	1.0	0.6
s2614ya	22/06/14	AO		EDT	Smith-Andover Land, Lincoln	MA	42.4255, -71.3074	1.0	0.6
s2615xx	22/06/15	PM	22:38	EDT	Saugerties, Ulster County	NY	42.1202 -73.9429	1.8	1.5
s2616ux	22/06/16	AO		EDT	Mattison Field, Concord	MA	42.4389, -71.3759	1.0	0.6
s2616xx	22/06/16	PM	23:07	EDT	Livingston, Columbia County	NY	42.1609 -73.7977	1.8	1.5
s2617xx	22/06/17	PM	01:33	EDT	Livingston, Columbia County	NY	42.153 -73.7918	1.8	1.5
s2617bw	22/06/17	CM, RD	19:34	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2618bw	22/06/18	CM, RD	19:43	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2618xx	22/06/18	PM	01:32	EDT	Clermont, Columbia County	NY	42.0789 -73.8324	1.8	1.5
s2619bw	22/06/19	CM, RD	19:41	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2620bw	22/06/20	CM, RD	19:37	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2620xx	22/06/20	PM	22:12	EDT	Cold Spring Rd, Columbia County	NY	42.148 -73.7854	1.8	1.5
s2621bw	22/06/21	CM, RD	19:34	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2621ug	22/06/21	AO		EDT	Mattison Field, Concord	MA	42.4432, -71.3741	1.0	0.6
s2621xx	22/06/21	PM	23:42	EDT	Milan, Dutchess County	NY	41.9941 -73.78	1.8	1.2
s2622xx	22/06/22	PM	23:28	EDT	Milan, Dutchess County	NY	42.0139 -73.8107	1.8	0.6
s2623bw	22/06/23	CM, RD	19:27	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2623ug	22/06/23	AO		EDT	Estabrook Woods	MA	42.4833, -71.3451	1.0	0.6
s2624xx	22/06/24	PM	01:40	EDT	Tongore Rd, Ulster County	NY	41.8763 -74.1439	1.8	1.2
s2624bw	22/06/24	CM, RD	19:31	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2625bw	22/06/25	CM, RD	19:26	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2625xx	22/06/25	PM	23:01	EDT	Livingston, Columbia County	NY	42.1502 -73.787	1.8	1.5
s2626bw	22/06/26	CM, RD	19:32	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2626ic	22/06/26	PB	21:53	EDT	Allegheny National Forest, Kellettsville	PA	41.5529157 -79.2531596	1.1	0.6
s2627mx	22/06/27	PB	21:56	EDT	Allegheny National Forest, Kellettsville	PA	41.5511784 -79.2505575	1.0	0.6
s2627xx	22/06/27	PM	22:21	EDT	Red Hook, Dutchess County	NY	41.9936 -73.7848	1.8	1.2
s2627bw	22/06/27	CM, RD	19:34	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2628mx	22/06/28	RSc	21:02	CDT	Fairfield	IA		1.5	1.1
s2628bw	22/06/28	CM, RD	19:36	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2629bw	22/06/29	CM, RD	19:39	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2630mx	22/06/30	PB	21:33	EDT	Allegheny National Forest, Kellettsville	PA	41.5511784 -79.2505575	0.9	1.3
s2630bw	22/06/30	CM, RD	19:39	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2630xx	22/06/30	PM	23:05	EDT	Red Hook, Dutchess County	NY	42.0517 -73.8759	1.8	1.8
s2701xx	22/07/01	PM	02:00	EDT	Red Hook, Dutchess County	NY	42.0669 -73.886	1.8	1.5
s2702xx	22/07/02	PM	00:49	EDT	Ulster County	NY	41.8844 -74.1186	1.8	2.1
s2705xx	22/07/05	PM	23:25	EDT	Ulster County	NY	41.8840 -74.1164	1.8	1.2
s2705ub	22/07/05	JD	21:21	EDT	Delaware Seashore State Park	DE		0.9	0.6
s2706mx	22/07/06	PB	21:24	EDT	Allegheny National Forest, Kellettsville	PA	41.5511784 -79.2505575	0.9	1.3
s2706ub	22/07/06	RJ	20:51	EDT	Delaware Seashore State Park	DE		0.9	0.6
s2707xx	22/07/07	PM	02:33	EDT	Cottkill Rd, Ulster County	NY	41.8539 -74.1227	1.8	1.2
s2708ip	22/07/08	PB	21:19	EDT	Kellettsville	PA	41.5509841 -79.2510015	1.3	0.6
s2708xx	22/07/08	BA	20:33	EDT	Sylvan Dell Farm, South Williamsport	PA	41.238036, -76.958556	0.9	0.6
s2709xx	22/07/09	BA	21:00	EDT	Lewisburg	PA	40.949425, -76.901225	0.9	0.6
s2710ip	22/07/10	PB	21:22	EDT	Kellettsville	PA	41.5509841 -79.2510015	1.4	0.6
s2711ip	22/07/11	PB	21:20	EDT	Kellettsville	PA	41.5509841 -79.2510015	1.4	0.6
s2713mx	22/07/13	RSc	22:16	CDT	Fairfield	IA		0.9	0.6
s2715bw	22/07/15	CM, RD	19:39	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2716bw	22/07/16	CM, RD	19:31	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2718bw	22/07/18	CM, RD	19:36	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2720bw	22/07/20	CM, RD	19:36	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2724bw	22/07/24	CM, RD	19:47	MST	Muleshoe Ranch CMA, Willcox	AZ		1.8	0.6
s2801ub	22/08/01	JD	20:40	EDT	Delaware Seashore State Park	DE		0.9	0.6
s2803ub	22/08/03	JD	20:38	EDT	Delaware Seashore State Park	DE		0.9	0.6
s2809ik	22/08/09	RS	20:30	MST	Pajarito Mountains, Coronado National Forest	AZ	31.393446 -111.090053	0.9	0.6